

NEW FOCUS OF INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS AGENDA

Romozonov Ulugbek Xoliyor-o'g'li

Master's student of International Law and Human Rights
at Tashkent State University of law
ramazanovulugbekk@gmail.com

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Abstract: The thesis delves into the institutional shift within international human rights law and how it has been received by state administrations in developing nations. Since the 1990s, there has been a notable proliferation of various institutional advancements across states, underscoring the rise of public human rights administrations in numerous countries. International law itself has undergone a transformation, moving beyond merely articulating norms and imposing constraints on states' actions. It now increasingly mandates institutional requirements aimed at bolstering state capabilities to effectively implement human rights commitments.

Keywords: Human rights protection, hallmark, human rights institutions, national protection system, international human rights norms, economic, social and cultural rights, political commitments, civil society, institutionalization, proliferation.

"When the Map of Freedom in lobby of the Freedom House building was first unveiled [in 1972...t]he government of Sweden [...] reacted to its surprisingly low rating in light of its high reputation for quality of life, social order, and freedom. [...Freedom House had to spell out] precisely why [it] warned about the trend toward 'bureaucratization' in Sweden and perhaps other free but highly bureaucratized countries."

Christopher Bradley (2015, 56)

Introduction

In 2002, United Nations (UN) Secretary-General Kofi Annan used his hallmark address on UN reform to underscore the importance of national institutions for human rights protection. For him (para. 50):

Building strong human rights institutions at the country level is what in the long run will ensure that human rights are protected and advanced in a sustained manner. The emplacement or enhancement of a national protection system in each country, reflecting international human rights norms, should therefore be a principal objective of the Organization.

The novelty is not that human rights commitments shall be primarily addressed by states, with support from the international community. This fundamental tenet was already expressed in 1948 by the Universal Declaration

of Human Rights. Its Article 22 foresaw that economic, social and cultural rights be realised “through national effort and international co-operation and in accordance with the organization and resources of each State.” The novelty lies in the fact that that onus on national efforts had so far been accompanied with a strong margin of appreciation safeguarding states’ discretion in the selection of implementation means, and even more in their organisational setup.

The Secretary-General’s formula builds upon the emergence of institutional prescriptions for organisational structures and processes at the national level. The 1993 World Conference on Human Rights in Vienna was pivotal in this respect and called for the establishment of NHRIs in line with the Principles relating to the status of national institutions (the Paris Principles) written by NHRIs in 1991 (UN 1993, para. 36). It also encouraged states to adopt National Human Rights Action Plans (NHRAPs) (para. 71). States requested the UN to invest in “programmes aiming at the establishment and strengthening of national legislation, national institutions and related infrastructures” (para. 34) and created the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR).

These developments were states’ political commitments rather than law, with a series of international conferences and their final declarations constituting milestones in the 1990s (see sub-Section 4.3.1). Such conferences acted as a meeting place of ideas, with civil society playing an increasing role and contributing to the promotion of specific institutional visions (see Gaer 1995).

1. Turn in states’ practice

In the 1990s, there was a significant increase in the spread of human rights institutions worldwide. One notable example is National Human Rights Institutions (NHRIs), which saw a remarkable growth from 28 in 1990 to 131 in 2015. This expansion was sparked by the endorsement of the Paris Principles at the Vienna Conference, leading to what scholars call a “global common shock.”

Additionally, new types of state actors emerged during this time. Human rights ministries, which were almost nonexistent before the 1990s, began to appear in countries like Mali, Morocco, and Pakistan. Today, 32 states have a dedicated human rights ministry.

Over the same period, specialised parliamentary human rights committees also proliferated. Only three countries had one prior to 1990. However, today,

71 additional countries have had at least one specialised parliamentary committee, all of them established in the period 1990-2008.¹

Furthermore, there were advancements in institutional techniques, such as the adoption of National Human Rights Action Plans (NHRAPs). Initially introduced by Australia in 1994, these plans have become widespread, with at least 114 plans in 71 countries adopted since 1993.

Another notable development is the use of measurements and human rights indicators to assess progress. This approach gained prominence following the 1993 Vienna Declaration, which encouraged states to use indicators to measure the realization of economic and social rights. Today, this technique is widely used and shapes the work of human rights institutions globally.

2. World order changes

The institutional turn cannot be seen in isolation from the deep transformations taking place in the 1990s. As Finnemore (1993) has shown, states adopt global models not because they accept the validity of the agenda, but because they associate it with what it means to be a modern state. The proliferation of state human rights institutions, too, can be analysed against the wider background of renewed perspectives on the characteristics of modern statehood.

First, the 1990s were marked by the end of the Cold War and the establishment of new democracies. In this context, the “logics and expectations of human rights coalesced into [...] the world’s only supernormativity” (Goodale 2013, 6), becoming the language of transitions, reforms and statebuilding. A number of works have associated the multiplication of both governmental and nongovernmental human rights actors with these historical developments (Mertus 2009, 6). The adhesion to human rights and its international oversight mechanisms has been assessed by some as a process of willingly restraining a country’s sovereignty to prevent returning to past authoritarian regimes (Moravcsik 2000). At a national level, human rights institutions may also signal the commitment to human rights while at the same time safeguarding sovereignty. For Cardenas (2014, 356-7):

the post-Cold War diffusion of NHRIs signals a historic normative shift: the implementation of international human rights norms, or their institutionalization in domestic structures, has become a measure of state legitimacy. [...] Neither human rights nor NHRIs displace state sovereignty,

¹ Sources: for committees established before 2004, IPU 2004; for committee established after 2004: PARLINE Databased of parliamentary human rights bodies, available at: <http://archive.ipu.org/parline-e/Instance-hr.asp>, accessed on 24/07/19.

or serve as an alternative focal point of authority. Rather, [they] constitute historically coevolving standards, infusing the state's sovereign legitimacy and authority with new meaning in a changing world. Indeed, if the Cold War saw the internationalization of human rights norms, the end of the Cold War gave way to their internalization.

Second, the emergence of a range of human rights administrations occurred while dominant views on institutions were undergoing drastic changes. In the 1980s and into the 1990s, new public management was the widely dominant paradigm for public administration. It prioritised the market and entailed a privatisation of state functions and a curtailing of public bureaucracies. The effects of those reforms, notably on social cohesion, were greatly criticised in the 1990s and were replaced by new governance approaches. At the core of the new ideology lay a vision of public service reform that changes the organisational form of the state, and especially the relations between the state, citizens, users and local communities (Clark 2004, 494).

Third-way political platforms (Giddens 1998) gave resonance to this model and were implemented by many Western governments (Canada, Germany, the Netherlands, Portugal, the United Kingdom, etc.) and some Global South countries (Brazil, Peru, South Africa, etc.) around the turn of the millennium. Third-way politics and new governance thinking therefore rehabilitated the importance of institutions, but did not return to welfare state bureaucracies of the 1960s where the states provide for services. New governance values collaboration and partnership, "active citizenship" and decision-making based on deliberations and learning through practice, with institutions organising these processes. A second key notion is that of "joined-up governance", which implies that all agencies and state actors should be coordinated (Newman 2006). While the objective of coordination is valued, it is also particularly elusive, and many reforms therefore focus on it. As stated by Rhodes and Tiernan (2015, 93), "coordination is the holy grail of modern government, ever sought, but always beyond reach."

In summary, the developments outlined in this section appear to be moving towards a common direction and potentially reinforcing each other. This suggests a significant departure from previous paradigms, though it might not be immediately apparent due to the prevailing institutional norms. Assertions such as the notion that enhancing national capacities through the expansion of NHRIs is the sole means to promote human rights starkly contrast with earlier viewpoints. Therefore, it is crucial to undertake a more comprehensive

investigation into these developments, particularly regarding their impact on the administrations of developing nations. With over two decades of experience, we are now in a position to evaluate the effectiveness of the institutionalization processes these models aimed to initiate. This section posits that these developments may be influenced by broader trends in new governance ideologies, potentially leading to a reevaluation of past approaches to human rights practices.

References:

1. Hibou (2015, 13-37) calls roughly the same set of characteristics “neoliberal bureaucracy”. One difference is that Hibou considers New Public Management has falling part of this trend. I follow Bezes (2007) and Dreschler (2005)’s definition. While I extensively engage with Hibou’s conceptual framework and use her terminology when referring to her scholarship, I prefer to refer to “neo-Weberianism”. “Neoliberalism” is connoted, and may mislead the readership as regards the research intentions, anticipating a left-wing critical scholarship denouncing a “project” imposed on society.
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3. Human Rights: New Perspectives, New Realities / Ed. by Admantia Pollis and Peter Schwab. Boulder, CO: Lynne Rienner, 2000. 259 p.
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